

Major new CS Track Report on Citizen Science reveals knowledge gaps

The CS Track team of researchers led by Christine Urban and Michael Strähle (Wissenschaftsladen Wien – Science Shop Vienna) has published a major in-depth report on Citizen Science in the form of a Conceptual Framework. This report includes a detailed literature review and introduces a new categorization and characterisation framework that will be used to shape the team’s policy recommendations and best practice manuals.

In the literature review, the research team investigated the different ways citizen science is defined and categorised as well as issues relating to the characteristics of citizen science frequently referenced in the research literature. This comprehensive report covers aspects such as the relationship between Citizen Science and the formal science system, visibility of Citizen Science along with other aspects such as economic considerations and the relationship between Citizen Science and education. The research team has identified a number of current knowledge gaps including cross-project comparative studies, the lack of information about citizen scientists’ socio-economic and educational background as well as the impact of citizen science projects and public engagement in science in general.

The report also introduces a new framework which can be used for classifying Citizen Science activities called the Activities & Dimensions Grid of Citizen Science (ADG-CS). This framework is based on four distinguishable types of citizen science activities, a) those providing input for research policy, b) those involving participation in research projects, c) those where the focus is on development and innovation, and d) those that are essentially school projects with minors.

Although the research team recognises that clear-cut categorisation of citizen science activities is not always feasible, they argue that this scheme provides useful guidelines that can be used to analyse selected citizen science activities in order to provide useful findings and recommendations.

Download the full deliverable [here](#).

Follow our work via our project website: cstrack.eu

Sign up for our newsletter: cstrack.eu/newsletter

Contact us: info@cstrack.eu

